
The importance of mass urban transport from a national security perspective

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Abstract

The article examines the energy consumption and importance of mass transport from the perspective of national security. All this is directly related to the way of life of people. The figure of mass public transport and its serious role in all these processes is included. The topic of the implementation of new technologies in cities and their realization is affected.

Key words: mass public transport, national security, energy consumption, cities.

Introduction

Nowadays, energy consumption grows every day. People around the world need more and more energy because innovation is being created in everyday life very quickly at an approximate steady pace. This circumstance puts people at risk in many of the sectors of activity. The transport sector is not an exception in this process. It uses a lot of energy because of its specific purpose and performance activity. It precisely operates the physical movement of people and goods from one place to another.

Material and methods.

The study is regarding the correlation between urban mass transit and national security. Concerning the scale and development of this mode of transport, an approach that is adequate in terms of a sustainable development of this kind of public relations and processes. A method of analysis and specificize has been used in terms of this type of public relations. The article starts a study how to implement and properly develop mass public transport on the wellbeing of the people. This study is one of the few of its kind exploring this type of social relations and their importance to people.

Results and Discussion

Sustainability on the process of transitioning to green energy

Green-powered motor vehicles or so-called renewable energy sources are increasingly entering the future. Many of the cars are currently powered by non-renewable energy sources. First, of course, they offer much cleaner and quality energy. The engines powered by such energy are also much quieter.

Historically, it has been known for many years that the aspects of this type of powered motor vehicle include limited period, regarding any charging in relation to the cost and mileage, which plays particular importance. They are also observed, they are characteristic of a different nature, which are not present in internal combustion engines.

Automobiles powered by electric batteries are priority and they are targeted humanity’s policy of developing new technologies, namely, to include in the future, most of the automobiles turn out to be power-driven by conventional source of fuel. It will become a big problem to find so much electricity and hence the energy dependency of the countries. Motor vehicles and their travel periods are linked by a serious daily mileage. The idea is that this energy needs to be produced, and this is a

serious and expensive process. It must be concluded that, in addition of the switch to green energy, which plays such a great importance, another issue must be raised also of very great importance regarding the target of those journeys and the distances. Electric batteries, for example, and technology are constantly evolving. Cryptocurrency (Petrova, N., p. 27-32) is gaining more strength and importance.

In fact, transport sector is tied to the constantly changing cost of the service. Depending on various factors, such as the cost of fuel the intra-urban mass transport is in the public's everyday life and social relations. It is very important that public transport (Vladimirov, I., p. 30) takes place with differences in the size and passenger capacity too.

Artificial intelligence, urban mass transport, private operators, and municipal enterprises

Regarding artificial intelligence, it is possible to count and calculate the passenger flow and it is also linked with the route schedules, which may be better not to go forward only through the central parts of the cities. It can be carried out in a variety of ways. The current route schedules, developed as quality and quantity in relation to passenger traffic, which are carried out by citizens in connection with their jobs, universities, position, schools for children and students and are therefore related to urban mass transport. All this is related to the tax (Petrova, N., p. 13-17) system of the private operators and municipal enterprises. As municipal enterprises can organize and control the activity. They are based on models from other cities that have the same number of passenger populations, route schedules. All these task models are mainly made in relation for the people wellbeing. This is a very important aspect of all the activity of the municipal enterprises that create for the organization of all these processes and the control of them. In general, GPS control centers can be controlled, by detecting buses on GPS devices. This is a very important aspect for several reasons. There are situations when all these important data is needed by the country or the local authority.

Public mass transport is an important part in the everyday life of the citizens. Passengers who use bus mass transport may be in different groups within some time periods. This whole model, which is so important in relation to the data presented above, leads to a conclusion of a very wide-ranging economic and social relation. Specifications in terms of this kind of mass transport should be noted in many studies. The discussion about the progress or possible regression of the mass bus transport is very important. It is expected that the population and of the cities all over the world will grow with fast pace. Schools and universities in the cities should be a positive indicator in relation to the increase in the population of public services. The organization of traffic have to be important part of the future engineer projects regarding the construction of roads or route schedules of buses, which are important connection with the monitoring of the passenger flow, which can be made by computer programs, technologies and specialists and experts in these very important field. Regarding difference in their geographical locations. This is important topic nowadays. All these documents, factual circumstances and data are linked together.

There needs to be innovative methods in public mass transport like the artificial intelligence (Petev, B., p. 56-59). There are special economical plans regarding funding bus mass transport in the cities of countries of EU. These programs should be implemented in terms of electric buses or bus powered by carbon energy and otherwise, which have zero emissions. It can be concluded that electric buses that are part of the inner-city transport, can be very efficient and cost-effective. Electric buses also are noiseless. This fact compared to diesel buses is also very important for the comfort of all passengers.

Conclusions

Climate change is one of the major challenges in the world.

Urban congestion and urban pollution present a serious issue regarding public health and the road traffic too. This kind of topics are very serious in transport sector. The successful implementation of

the green energy is very important topic. The sustainable development is a key element in the process of developing of new technologies.

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